

Original Article

Exploring the Need for Inclusive Teaching and Challenges of Students with Different Abilities to Receive Higher Education in the Public Sector Universities

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Abstract

This research gained a motivation by the need to explore how the workplace environment affects university faculty ' stress level. The study focused on the physical surroundings, social dynamics, and organizational culture, and their significant impact on how faculty learn and perceive themselves. The study explored various elements of the university settings, such as on-campus facilities, interpersonal connections, and institutional sports area and their effect on faculty ' stress level. The findings indicated that a safe workplace environment helps to decrease stress of faculty, suggesting that workplace modifications can create a more encouraging learning environment and increase faculty efficacy. The researchers reviewed literature from different websites, books, and articles. A qualitative method was used to explore the effectiveness of the workplace environment on university faculty ' stress level. Therefore, semi-structured interviews were used with 20 teachers to collect qualitative data. Convenient and purposive sampling was used to gather data from 20 teachers in university. The study found that a positive workplace environment benefits faculty learning ability. It was concluded that teachers need to be aware of faculty' problems. Recommendations were provided to university authorities and security staff to enhance high level security to make safe the workplace environment.

Keywords: Differently Able Students, Support, Higher Education, Educational Experiences, Diverse Learning

Introduction and Context of the Study

The education system overlooked the requirements of children with disabilities. Whether it's providing infrastructure support or fostering an inclusive school climate, Schools have found themselves ill-equipped to accommodate students with disabilities. However, several government policies for the disabled in Pakistan have attempted to solve this issue over time. Mahawariya and Yadav (2021) referred to the fact that a differently abled student requires specific attention owing to their unique learning talents, medical conditions, or physical disabilities. Institutions must priorities providing facilities that support intellectual, academic and cultural growth for all students (Bromer & Crawford, 2022).

Moreover, students with cognitive, psychological, or emotional impairments will no longer be referred to as "disabled." We must now refer to them as "differently abled." The policy is well-intentioned, yet it damages many of the students it was designed to aid. The same may be true for many of our learning challenged students. To refer to someone as "differently abled" may incorrectly assign useful attributes to them that would provide them with an

JOURNAL OF
SOCIAL HORIZONS

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How to Cite:

Salamat, L., Saleem, A., Akhter, N. (2024). Exploring the Need for Inclusive Teaching and Challenges of Students with Different Abilities to Receive Higher Education in Public Sector Universities. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 1(2), 1-10.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15101211>

advantage they do not really enjoy, while also diminishing the real problems they face and work around or overcome in order to achieve and present themselves as capable (Stern, 2020). Class (2023) argued that using polite and proper language when discussing disability is an important component of disability rights here are some best practices for vocabulary and avoiding the term "differently abled."

Gilbert and Rajan (2020) higher education are widely recognized as a philosophy for achieving fairness, justice and excellent education for all children, particularly those who have traditionally been excluded from mainstream school due to disability, ethnicity, gender, or other characteristics. Some countries have effectively implemented higher education, while others are still working towards it. Higher education as the process of addressing and responding to all learners' various needs by boosting involvement in learning and eliminating exclusion within and outside of school. The second half of the 21st century, higher education has become a popular technique for educating pupils with special needs. This education strategy aims to improve educational opportunities for individuals with special needs (Yuksel et al., 2021).

Ludago (2020) discussed that children with special disabilities face a variety of educational barriers. These learning challenges are frequently related to inclusion and include a variety of characteristics such as assessment quality, placement, service quality, interaction between students with disabilities and students, socio-cultural milieu and facility accessibility. One of the most important parts of implementing higher education effectively is service quality. Belay and Yihun (2020) discussed that higher education involves admitting all children to normal schools without discrimination. It is important to accommodate the many needs and interests of all learners, rather than separate them based on their strengths or capabilities. Higher education involves more than just placing children with special needs in mainstream schools.

Disability can be viewed as a natural and useful human experience with strengths and virtues that everyone encounters at some point in life, rather than a condition or issue. Individuals are referred to as 'differently abled', highlighting their strengths rather than their impairments (Beer et al., 2023). This study is intended to understand meaning-making in higher education by analysing the psychological experiences of differently abled first-year students. The higher education as a teaching paradigm in which all students, regardless of aptitude, learn together in one setting (Learn, 2021).

Picard (2015) discussed that the kids with impairments, the educational environment may provide unique obstacles that must be accommodated and considered. Mokobane (2010) supported the view that higher education aims to provide equal learning opportunities for all learners. However, there are still disparities, labelling and stigmatisation of differently abled learners in inclusive schools. Non-discriminatory unitary system to promote educational opportunity and mutual respect among all students in schools. The authors emphasise the importance of addressing previous inequities, recognising that everyone can learn and that learning disparities should not be viewed as deficits.

A significant obstacle to higher education is the mindset of parents and educators regarding children with disabilities. Inclusion would remain a pipe dream that would never materialize if students have a bad attitude about including students with special needs in regular classes and if they don't think these students can be educated in regular schools. Some parents of normal children appear to be against sending their kids to integrated schools, where kids with and without disabilities attend classes together. They claim that this will negatively impact the education of their kids and that their regular kids will copy the bad manners and behaviors of the disabled kids (Khan, 2014).

There are specific issues with parents' and educators' unfavorable views and actions toward the abilities of people with disabilities and kids to get knowledge. These obstacles can be addressed by increasing community understanding of human rights and showcasing inspiring tales of disabled children thriving in inclusive classrooms and beyond. Other potential strategies include encouraging action research and critical pedagogy among educators and helping impaired students communicate their goals and take part in planning procedures (Yuksel et al., 2021). In order to address the concerns of parents and more generally, to ensure just and democratic governance arrangements, it is imperative that monitoring bodies such as parent-students associations exist and that parents of disabled children are appropriately represented in such entitlements. There will be obstacles and possibilities along the long and winding road towards higher education. It is unrealistic for any government to transition from special or cohesive approaches to inclusive ones quickly (Khan, 2014).

Statement of Problem

Differently abled children find it difficult to integrate into mainstream classrooms in Pakistan, despite the global emphasis on higher education. It is notable that discrimination and exclusion can be sustained by negative attitudes or insufficient support from students, which might hinder these kids' academic progress. For the purpose of identifying barriers to and facilitators of higher education, students' intentions to serve students with disabilities are essential. Therefore, the study needs to explore the opportunities and challenges with inclusiveness of differently able students with in receiving higher education at universities.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it seeks to identify some of the real, practical, implementation-related problems that effect inclusive education in universities in higher education in Pakistan. The main cause of these problems is the important stakeholders in the education sector's lack of knowledge, comprehension and information sharing regarding disability issues in general and actionable disability issues in particular. Educators, parents, students and administrators are some of these stakeholders. This understanding may help guide government policy and implementation, as well as serve as a baseline for future studies on higher education in the nation.

Research Objectives of the Study

There were the following objectives of the study:

1. To explore the support for differently able students receiving for their higher education.
2. To Investigate educational opportunities for students with diverse abilities.
3. To investigate the challenges experienced by differently abled students in receiving higher education.

Research Questions

There were the following questions in this study:

1. What is the support available for differently able students receiving for their higher education?
2. What are educational opportunities for students with diverse abilities?
3. How do the students perceive the challenges experienced by differently able students in receiving higher education?

Delimitations

This study was delimited to the University students because of the time constraints and shortage of resources for data collection.

Review oof the Related Literature

A common definition of disability is any physical, mental, or psychological ailment that restricts an individual's activity. Its significance varies depending on the individual and the situation A student whose capacity to learn differs from other students for a variety of reasons, such as mental health or condition, learning disability, or physical handicap, is referred to as a differently abled or particularly abled learner (Yadav, 2021). The word "physical disability" is a general term that includes both innate and acquired disabilities, as well as a variety of illnesses and disorders. A physical disability is defined as a physical handicap that significantly and permanently limits a student's capacity to engage in regular activities, like learning. A person with a mild physical impairment may experience difficulties with their mobility, such as difficulty climbing stairs and will require assistance or walking aids to move around. A significant physical handicap will prevent a person from walking and require assistance to get around (Pirzara, 2023). For their learning to take place effectively, students with physical limitations must be placed in a supportive classroom or learning environment. The term "disability" refers to a variety of aspects in human cognition, including limitations, handicaps, incapacity and obstacles that affect a sizeable portion of a country's populace (Yadav, 2021).

According to (Emmanuel, 2018) this is any loss or decrease in functional ability (because to impairment) to carry out an activity in the way or within the range that is typically regarded as typical for a human being in the given cultural context. People with disabilities may also be prevented from participating on an equal basis in the regular activities of the community due to a lack of opportunity. These could be obstacles to full involvement that are social or physical. Disability is the result of an impairment, which can be developmental, emotional, sensory, cognitive, mental, physical or a combination of these. A disability may arise from an accident or sickness later in life, or it may originate from difficulties during childbirth (Kabuta, 2014).

The concept of disability is multifaceted and has evolved significantly over time. Historically, disability was often viewed through a medical lens, focusing on the individual's impairment and its limitations. This perspective, rooted in the early 20th century, emphasized the need for treatment and rehabilitation (Bickenbach, 2022). For instance, the medical model posits that disability is a defect within an individual that needs to be fixed or managed (Oliver, 1996). This model can lead to a focus on what people with disabilities lack, rather than considering how societal structures might contribute to their challenges.

However, the social model is not without its criticisms. Some argue that it may downplay the personal experiences and challenges faced by individuals with disabilities (Shakespeare, 2006). Critics suggest that while societal barriers are significant, individual impairments can also impact a person's life in ways that are not solely attributable to social factors. This perspective calls for a more nuanced understanding that integrates both medical and social aspects of disability. The biopsychosocial model of disability offers a middle ground by combining elements of both the medical and social models. This model considers how biological, psychological and social factors interact to shape an individual's experience of disability (Engel, 2019). It recognizes that while societal barriers play a critical role, individual health conditions and personal experiences also influence one's interaction with the world.

In addition to these models, the concept of disability is also informed by cultural perspectives. For example, in some cultures, disability may be seen through a spiritual or moral lens, which can affect how individuals with disabilities are perceived and treated (Goodley, 2018). Understanding these cultural contexts is important for developing more inclusive and respectful approaches to disability. The intersectionality framework further enriches our understanding of disability by highlighting how it intersects with other social identities such as race, gender and socioeconomic status. This approach acknowledges that individuals with disabilities do not experience their disability in isolation but in conjunction with other aspects of their identity (Crenshaw, 2012). For instance, a disabled person who is also a member of a racial minority may face compounded barriers that are distinct from those experienced by disabled individuals who are not part of racial minorities.

Educational institutions are also pivotal in shaping attitudes toward differently able students. Higher education practices that integrate students with disabilities into mainstream classrooms can foster a more equitable learning environment and challenge negative stereotypes (Florian, 2018). By promoting inclusivity and diversity, schools can help cultivate a more informed and empathetic society. Effective policies must address both physical accessibility and social attitudes to ensure that individuals with disabilities have equal opportunities (Harris, 2001). This includes advocating for laws that support workplace accommodations, accessible housing and equitable healthcare services. Finally, personal narratives and lived experiences of individuals with disabilities are essential for understanding the complexity of differently able students. These narratives provide valuable insights into how differently able students is experienced on a day-to-day basis and can inform more empathetic and effective approaches to support and inclusion (Hahn, 2002).

It is crucial to take into account the facilities offered by universities, which must meet the needs of students with disabilities. Given the types of disabilities exhibited by the kids in the classroom, great consideration should be given to the design of the classrooms. Depending on the range of disabilities represented in the class, the instructor may need to make particular adjustments for each student. For instance, pupils who are completely blind, deaf, or physically challenged may require considerable modifications to the curriculum or instructional accommodations. Environmental factors such as the classroom's layout, design and accessibility should be taken into account (Bilić, 2017). According to ministry of social welfare, in order to ensure that no applicant or student is denied an opportunity because of a handicap, IBA works to grant equal access to facilities, activities, learning and assessment to all applicants and students. All incoming and continuing students with disabilities are covered by this policy.

Alvi (2023) to properly meet the particular educational needs of pupils with disabilities, President Dr Arif Alvi has asked for the development of a curriculum for these students. He emphasized that in addition to providing support and assistance, the curriculum should address how society should behave toward persons with disabilities, as these individuals deal with a variety of challenges daily, such as prejudice. The best approach to involve every student in the curriculum is to present the broad curriculum while accommodating their individual learning preferences. When it comes to how their kids learn, parents are experts. Parents and schools need to collaborate without the assistance of the other, neither the parent nor the school can properly educate a child (Devid, 2022).

Few people with disabilities were enrolled in the institution's programs since the majority lacked the necessary entry-level qualifications. There is no difference in the likelihood of higher education between people without impairments and those with disabilities. To change the current low enrolment at the tertiary level, there was a need to improve awareness, provide more assistance and provide more enabling structures for people with disabilities at the primary level (Kabuta, 2014). For many students, even the regular ones, this is a significant setback. However, the institution has created a staggered payment plan that enables students to spread out their three-month tuition payment. Additionally, students are directed to a few financial institutions that set up loan programs for students who are employed and have some form of collateral. This excludes a possible proportion of disabled students who may possess academic aptitude but lack employment opportunities. They find themselves in a worse condition than students with able bodies (Kabuta,2014).

Jazeel (2017) stated that students with differently abled should also have equitable access to education, higher education and other possibilities. All students who attend and are accepted by their neighbourhood institutions in age-appropriate, regular courses and who are supported to study, contribute and participate in all elements of the school's life are said to have access to higher education, also known as inclusion in education. One of the fundamental rights of an individual with disabilities is this. Most of these "unreached" or marginalized disabled children have been kept cooped up in their homes by their parents and relatives, depriving them of their rights to education, a dignified life in society and other social, economic and political advantages. It is pitiful that they cannot even be allowed to explore their hidden potential and hone their skills and abilities in order to find a means of income (Zafit, 2019).

Numerous changes resulted from activities that seemed to be a way to address the physical and mental issues that differently abled people were facing during the study. The term "differentially abled" refers to a state in which a person's mental growth is stopped or incomplete and is particularly marked by sub-normal intellect. When children with disabilities attend school alongside their peers without disabilities, they see students without disabilities in the settings where they are required, which helps them acquire social skills appropriate for their age. Students with impairments can thrive in demanding environments in integrated settings (Ceo, 2022). As a result, these kids gain increasingly advanced abilities and become more independent. Allowing them to participate in activities that other students do can also help them form friendships and cultivate a more positive self-image. Students of special education and general education can both benefit from teaching in integrated configurations. Students in general education have the chance to acquire knowledge about special education and disabilities. Because they work with pupils who are typically developing on a regular basis, special education students have more reasonable expectations for their students. Furthermore, the students are able to share ideas on lesson plans and pedagogical approaches, which broadens their skill set (Jeo, 2020). A learner who learns from within many physical and mental limitations. When he arrives at school, he can see that it is difficult to adapt to his difficulties and study. The main reasons for this are age, mood and other physical characteristics. As a result, the child ends up learning (Khan, 2024).

The literature on higher education for differently abled students reveals both progress and significant gaps that present both opportunities and challenges. One major gap is the limited research on the long-term outcomes and career trajectories of students with disabilities post-graduation. While there is a growing body of work focused on the experiences of these students during their academic careers, there is less empirical evidence on how higher education impacts their employment opportunities, career advancement and overall quality of life. Addressing this gap could provide valuable insights into how higher education institutions can better support students with disabilities in transitioning to the workforce and achieving their career goals.

Another notable gap is the lack of comprehensive studies on the intersectionality of differently able students with other social identities, such as race, gender and socioeconomic status. Current research often overlooks how these intersecting identities can compound the challenges faced by differently abled students. For instance, a disabled student who is also a member of a racial or ethnic minority may experience unique barriers that are not fully addressed by existing support systems. Exploring these intersections can help create more nuanced and inclusive support structures that address the diverse needs of students from various backgrounds. The literature also reveals a need for more on the shortage of research focusing on the perspectives and experiences of differently abled students themselves. Including student perspectives in research can provide a clearer understanding of their actual experiences, preferences and unmet needs, thereby enabling institutions to tailor their approaches more closely to the realities faced by these students. The interview included nine items covering various aspects of the

study. First, the purpose and significance of the research were explained. In addition, participants' rights and some tips for answering questions were mentioned. Finally, data collection process completed within 4 weeks. Data collection was conducted personally by researcher throughout the university by using purposefully.

Thematic Findings

The following were the main themes that emerged from the and interview and focus group data:

1. Perceived Challenges Faced by Differently abled Students
2. Exploring Opportunities in Receiving Education for Differently abled Students
3. Opportunities Differently abled Students in Receiving Education
4. Perception of Students Supporting Differently Abled Students' Education

Theme 1: Perceived Challenges Faced by Differently Abled Students

Participants were inquired about the Perceived Challenges Faced by Differently abled Students. They were asked and asked about using Faced by Differently abled Students. Hence this data indicates Specialized resources refer to materials, equipment and expertise that are unique and tailored for specific purposes, while technology systems that enable the utilization of these resources in a more efficient and effective manner. On the other hand, few participants had two years of teaching experience.

According to my idea furthermore, access to specialized resources and technology can also lead to improvements in efficiency and productivity (DAS2).

Hence, this data indicates, in manufacturing, advanced machinery and automation technologies can streamline production processes, reduce errors and increase output. In the field of agriculture, specialized equipment and techniques can help farmers maximize yields, minimize waste and ensure food security.

Hence, this data shows that the in the field of medicine, access to advanced medical equipment and expertise can lead to the development of new treatments and procedures that address diseases and conditions that were previously untreatable. Similarly, in the field of engineering, specialized materials and tools can help in the design and construction of structures that are more resilient and sustainable.

Subtheme 2: Social Inclusion and Acceptance

The collected data showed that half of the participants Social Inclusion and Acceptance. Most of the participants think that it is not an easy task to handle Social Inclusion and Acceptance. Hence, this data indicates, Inclusive societies promote a sense of belonging and understanding among diverse individuals, fostering a more harmonious and supportive environment for everyone. Therefore, the Data indicates that's it aims to eliminate barriers that prevent certain groups from fully engaging in society, such as discrimination, prejudice and lack of access to resources. By promoting social inclusion, communities can benefit from the unique contributions and perspectives of every individual, leading to stronger relationships and a more vibrant social fabric.

Acceptance, on the other hand, goes hand in hand with social inclusion by promoting tolerance and understanding of differences among individuals (DAS1).

Hence this Data indicates, Acceptance requires recognizing and respecting the diversity of identities, beliefs and lifestyles present in society. It involves embracing people for who they are without judgment or prejudice, creating a more welcoming and inclusive environment for all.

When social inclusion and acceptance are actively promoted, individuals are more likely to feel secure, respected and valued within their communities (DAS9).

Hence this data indicates that, This, in turn, can lead to increased social cohesion, improved mental well-being and enhanced overall quality of life for all members of society.

Subtheme 3: Physical Accessibility in Educational Institutions

The collected data showed that all the participants used Physical accessibility in educational institutions. This data indicates that this includes providing ramps, elevators, accessible bathrooms and designated parking spaces, among others, to enable students with disabilities to navigate the campus and participate fully in academic and social activities. Hence, this data show that, by providing ramps and elevators, schools and universities make it possible for students in wheelchairs or with mobility impairments to move around the campus independently. Accessible

classrooms and lecture halls ensure that all students can participate in discussions and engage with the learning material without feeling excluded.

Moreover, physical accessibility is not just about meeting legal requirements or fulfilling a moral obligation; it also promotes a sense of belonging and acceptance among students with disabilities (DAS13).

Hence this data indicates When educational institutions prioritize accessibility, they signal to students with disabilities that their needs are valued and accommodated. This can have a positive impact on their self-esteem and confidence, leading to better academic performance and overall well-being.

Theme 2: Exploring Opportunities in Receiving Education for Differently abled Students

Differently abled Students believed that support and interventions can address individual strengths and weaknesses, foster motivation and promote positive outcomes. Hence Each student has different abilities, backgrounds and learning styles and a one-size-fits-all approach may not be effective in meeting their needs. Tailored interventions take into consideration these individual differences and provide customized learning experiences that cater to the specific needs of each student. Another participant pointed that:

Moreover, tailored educational interventions can help address barriers to learning that students may face. These interventions can provide additional support for students with learning difficulties, disabilities, or socio-economic challenges (DAS23).

Hence, this data indicates that by collecting data on student performance, educators can identify areas where students may need additional help and tailor interventions accordingly. Other participants stated that:

Furthermore, tailored support systems can also involve collaboration among students, parents and other stakeholders to coordinate efforts and provide holistic support for students (DAS17).

This data indicates, by working together, educators and parents can ensure that students receive consistent and coordinated support in both the school environments. These programs aim to provide practical knowledge and hands-on experience that are directly relevant to specific occupations ensuring that individuals are well-equipped with the necessary skills and expertise to excel in their chosen field. Hence, this data indicates that, unlike traditional academic programs that may provide theoretical knowledge, vocational training programs offer hands-on experience that is directly applicable to the job market. This helps individuals to develop the specific skills and competencies required to perform well in their chosen field. Another participant stated that:

These programs often offer a range of options for individuals to choose from, allowing them to tailor their training to suit their interests and career goals (DAS16).

Hence, these programs often offer a range of options for individuals to choose from, allowing them to tailor their training to suit their interests and career goals. This flexibility is particularly valuable for individuals who may not excel in traditional academic settings or who are looking to transition into a new career. Other participants stated that:

Skills development and vocational training also play a crucial role in addressing skills gaps in the workforce. This not only benefits individuals by increasing their employability (T1).

Hence this data indicates that by providing individuals with the training and expertise needed for in-demand occupations, these programs help to bridge the gap between the skills that employers are looking for and the skills that job seekers possess.

The collected data showed that most of the participants knew about the of Advocacy and policy changes benefiting differently abled students. They believed it is a process of looking back on past experiences to analyse, examine and generate new meaning. Hence, this data show that, by advocating for the rights of these students, individuals and organizations have been able to bring about important policy changes that address the specific needs of differently abled students.

Advocates for differently abled students have worked tirelessly to ensure that policies are in place to support this model of education, which allows these students to learn alongside their peers in mainstream classrooms (DAS24).

This data indicates that, advocates for differently abled students have worked tirelessly to ensure that policies are in place to support this model of education, which allows these students to learn alongside their peers in mainstream classrooms. Hence this data shows that, these accommodations may include assistive technologies, specialized instruction and additional resources to help these students succeed academically. By advocating for these policies, individuals and organizations have helped to level the playing field for differently abled students and ensure that they have the tools they need to thrive in the classroom.

Theme 3: Opportunities Differently Abled Students in Receiving Education

The data show that Individualized learning plans and accommodations are essential tools in the education system for supporting students with diverse needs and abilities. These plans are designed to cater to the unique learning styles, strengths and challenges of each individual student to ensure that they have equal opportunities to succeed academically. Another participant stated that:

By identifying a student's strengths and weaknesses, educators can create personalized learning goals and strategies to support their academic growth (DAS26).

Hence, this data show that the by identifying a student's strengths and weaknesses, educators can create personalized learning goals and strategies to support their academic growth. This approach not only helps students achieve academic success but also boosts their confidence and self-esteem. Hence, this data indicates that, this could include alternative formats for assignments, extra time for tests, or specialized equipment to support students with disabilities. By providing accommodations, educators are able to level the playing field and ensure that all students have an equal chance to learn and succeed.

Moreover, individualized learning plans and accommodations foster a positive and inclusive learning environment where every student feels valued and supported (DAS9).

This data show that, by tailoring instruction to meet the needs of each individual student and providing necessary accommodations, educators can support a diverse range of learners and create an inclusive and supportive learning environment. Ultimately, these tools help to promote academic success, boost confidence and foster a sense of belonging among students.

Subtheme 2: Equitable Access to Quality Education

This data indicates that, this means addressing barriers such as financial constraints, geographical location and discrimination that may prevent some individuals from accessing education. Efforts should be made to provide equal resources and opportunities to all students, regardless of their socioeconomic status or background.

Moreover, quality education should be a priority in order to ensure that all individuals receive the skills and knowledge necessary to succeed in life (DAS3).

Hence, Quality education goes beyond just academic achievement and should also focus on developing critical thinking skills, creativity and problem-solving abilities. Students play a crucial role in delivering quality education and efforts should be made to support and train educators to provide the best possible learning experience for all students. Hence, this data show that This includes addressing issues such as segregation, discrimination and lack of resources in underserved communities. Policies and programs should be implemented to level the playing field and provide equal opportunities for all students.

Subtheme 3: Transition Planning for Post-Education Opportunities

The collected data showed that most of the participants about Transition planning for post-education opportunities. This data indicates that, this phase could include further education, vocational training, employment, or any other opportunities that align with the individual's goals and aspirations. Transition planning is vital for individuals to achieve their full potential and lead fulfilling lives. Other Participants Stated that:

One of the key components of transition planning is goal setting. Individuals need to identify their long-term goals and aspirations, as well as short-term objectives that will help them achieve these goals (DAS28).

Hence, this data indicates that, Individuals need to identify their long-term goals and aspirations, as well as short-term objectives that will help them achieve these goals. By setting clear and achievable goals, individuals can create a roadmap for their transition and make informed decisions about their post-education opportunities.

Hence, an assessment helps individuals identify their strengths, preferences, interests and needs, which can be used to determine the most suitable post-education opportunities. Individuals need to have a clear understanding of their skills and abilities to make informed choices about their future.

Collaboration can also help in identifying resources, support systems and opportunities that can assist the individual in achieving their goals (DAS10).

By working together, all parties can ensure that the individual's needs and aspirations are accurately assessed and addressed. Collaboration can also help in identifying resources, support systems and opportunities that can assist the individual in achieving their goals.

Theme 4: Perception of Students Supporting Differently Abled Students Education

Participants were inquired about the Perception of Students Supporting Differently Abled Students' Education. They were asked and probed to talk about the Perception of Students Supporting Differently Abled Students' Education. The collected data showed that most of the participants easily grow up our knowledge and another Training and professional development for higher education. Hence, this data show that to achieve this goal, training and professional development play a crucial role in equipping educators with the necessary knowledge, skills and attitudes to create inclusive learning environments. Other participants stated that:

Training and professional development for higher education involve continuous learning and improvement to meet the diverse needs of students (DAS25).

Hence, this data show that Educators must understand the principles of higher education, such as diversity, equity and belonging, to foster a supportive and inclusive learning environment. They need to be aware of different teaching strategies, accommodations and adaptations to meet the individual needs of students with disabilities or learning differences. This data indicate that These programs may include workshops, seminars, online courses and conferences that focus on topics such as behaviour management and assistive technology. By participating in such training, educators can improve their ability to support all students in their classrooms effectively. A participant stated that:

Moreover, training and professional development can also help educators address biases, stereotypes and prejudices that may hinder inclusive practices (DAS10).

By promoting self-reflection and cultural competence, educators can create inclusive classrooms where all students feel valued, respected and supported. The participants were inquired about skills that can be developed in the Attitudinal shifts towards embracing diversity This data show that diversity encompasses differences in race, ethnicity, gender, religion, sexuality, socioeconomic background and more. Embracing diversity means acknowledging, appreciating and valuing these differences to create a more inclusive and equitable society. One participant noted that:

Embracing diversity fosters creativity and innovation, leading to better outcomes in various fields such as business, education and healthcare (DAS10).

Hence, this data show that When people from different backgrounds come together, they can bring unique insights and solutions to complex problems. Embracing diversity fosters creativity and innovation, leading to better outcomes in various fields such as business, education and healthcare.

As people become more conscious of systemic inequalities and discrimination, there is a greater push for inclusivity and equal representation (DAS24).

Hence, as people become more conscious of systemic inequalities and discrimination, there is a greater push for inclusivity and equal representation. Embracing diversity helps to dismantle barriers and create a more equitable society where everyone has the opportunity to thrive.

Furthermore, globalization has made the world more interconnected than ever before. As people interact with individuals from different cultures and backgrounds, they become more open-minded and accepting of diversity (DAS20).

Therefore, as people interact with individuals from different cultures and backgrounds, they become more open-minded and accepting of diversity. Embracing diversity is essential for building strong relationships and fostering understanding between people from various walks of life.

Education and awareness are key in promoting attitudinal shifts towards embracing diversity, as they help individuals recognize the importance of inclusivity and the benefits of diversity (DAS27).

Hence, this data show that Attitudes and beliefs that perpetuate discrimination and prejudice must be actively challenged and replaced with values of respect, acceptance and empathy. Education and awareness are key in promoting attitudinal shifts towards embracing diversity, as they help individuals recognize the importance of inclusivity and the benefits of diversity.

Theme 5: Creating Inclusive Classroom Environments

The participants were inquired about the Creating Inclusive Classroom Environments. They were asked and probed to all about the Creating Inclusive Classroom Environments. Hence, this data show that Special education professionals bring valuable knowledge and experience in working with students with disabilities, while general education students offer insights into the curriculum and classroom management. By collaborating, both parties can learn from each other and develop effective strategies to support students with diverse learning needs.

Special education professionals can provide valuable guidance on implementing individualized education plans (IEPs) and accommodations (DAS10).

Hence, this data indicates that Special education professionals can provide valuable guidance on implementing individualized education plans and accommodations, while general education students can adapt their teaching practices to meet the needs of all students.

Discussions

Data from interview responses reveals that students feel in the classroom. The syllabus they had to teach was based on the content covered, but the exams set for students rewarded the correct rendering of that content. A student whose capacity to learn differs from other students for a variety of reasons, such as mental health or condition, learning differently able students, or physical handicap, is referred to as a differently abled or particularly abled learner is similar to (Yadav,2021). Access to specialized resources and technology is crucial in today's modern world as it plays a significant role in driving innovation, improving efficiency and ultimately enhancing the quality of life. Specialized resources refer to materials, equipment and expertise that are unique and tailored for specific purposes, while technology systems that enable the utilization of these resources in a more efficient and effective manner.

The primary concepts of this action plan are impairment, handicap and differently able students. These ideas were applied in the assessment of the overall state of impairment. An anomaly in a human's physiological, psychological, or anatomical functioning or structure is referred to as an impairment in this context. While handicap refers to a person's disadvantage resulting from impairment and differently able students, which obstructs or prevents an individual from achieving the state that is considered normal for human beings, differently able students stem from impairment, which refers to the inability to carry out tasks and activities is similar to (Karim, 2019). Furthermore, access to specialized resources and technology can also lead to improvements in efficiency and productivity. For example, in manufacturing, advanced machinery and automation technologies can streamline production processes, reduce errors and increase output. In the field of agriculture, specialized equipment and techniques can help farmers maximize yields, minimize waste and ensure food security.

Likewise, to (Emran, 2018), this is any loss or decrease in functional ability (because to impairment) to carry out an activity in the way or within the range that is typically regarded as typical for a human being in the given cultural context. People with disabilities may also be prevented from participating on an equal basis in the regular activities of the community due to a lack of opportunity. These could be obstacles to full involvement that are social or physical. Social inclusion and acceptance are fundamental pillars of a cohesive society where all individuals feel valued, respected and part of the community. Inclusive societies promote a sense of belonging and understanding among diverse individuals, fostering a more harmonious and supportive environment for everyone.

Depending on the range of disabilities represented in the class, the instructor may need to make particular adjustments for each student. For instance, pupils who are completely blind, deaf, or physically challenged may require considerable modifications to the curriculum or instructional accommodations. Environmental factors such as the classroom's layout, design and accessibility should be taken into account is similar to (Bilić, 2017). Differently able students are the result of an impairment, which can be developmental, emotional, sensory,

cognitive, mental, physical, or a combination of these. A differently able students may arise from an accident or sickness later in life, or it may originate from difficulties during childbirth is similar to (Kabuta, 2014). Social inclusion refers to the process of ensuring that all individuals, regardless of their backgrounds, identities, or circumstances, have equal opportunities to participate in social, economic and political activities. It aims to eliminate barriers that prevent certain groups from fully engaging in society, such as discrimination, prejudice and lack of access to resources is similar to (Khan, 2021). By promoting social inclusion, communities can benefit from the unique contributions and perspectives of every individual, leading to stronger relationships and a more vibrant social fabric.

Similar to (Alsov, 2023)., social inclusion and acceptance is essential for communities to actively engage in promoting diversity, equity and inclusivity through education, policies and initiatives that celebrate differences and foster empathy and understanding. By creating spaces that welcome and empower individuals of all backgrounds, communities can build stronger connections, foster mutual respect and create a more cohesive and resilient society for everyone to thrive in. moreover, the key benefits of physical accessibility in educational institutions is that it allows students with disabilities to access quality education without facing unnecessary barriers. By providing ramps and elevators, schools and universities make it possible for students in wheelchairs or with mobility impairments to move around the campus independently. Accessible classrooms and lecture halls ensure that all students can participate in discussions and engage with the learning material without feeling excluded is similar to (Ahmad, 2018). Additionally, advocacy efforts have also led to the implementation of policies that provide necessary accommodations and support services for differently abled students. These accommodations may include assistive technologies, specialized instruction and additional resources to help these students succeed academically. By advocating for these policies, individuals and organizations have helped to level the playing field for differently abled students and ensure that they have the tools they need to thrive in the classroom.

The challenging circumstances have a negative effect on the weakened students' academic achievement. Due to the challenges, they encountered, students with physical limitations studying in an unsuitable learning environment did badly in their academics. Among the challenges they faced were lengthy walking distances, restricted access to educational resources and mounting stairs in buildings. Several studies conducted in developing nations have consistently found that there is a dearth of knowledge regarding the support services available to impaired students in higher education is similar to (Kabuta, 2014). Another crucial aspect of transition planning is assessment. An assessment helps individuals identify their strengths, preferences, interests and needs, which can be used to determine the most suitable post-education opportunities. It is essential for individuals to have a clear understanding of their skills and abilities to make informed choices about their future.

In online forums discussing the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals, for instance, people with disabilities expressed that they did not feel included in the decision-making process regarding these issues. This is partly due to the prevalence of medical imagery associated with them, which keeps people from realizing that people with disabilities have a stake in a variety of social problems addressed. About the way people with disabilities, including children and youth with disabilities, are portrayed, there are two ways to look at it: either as "normal," with people with disabilities, including children and youth with disabilities, facing social issues brought on by environmental realities or health issues like everyone else, or as negative, medical imagery with "their differently able students" in need of prevention or fixing is similar to (Salvatore and Wolbrig, 2021).

Most of these "unreached" or marginalized disabled children have been kept cooped up in their homes by their parents and relatives, depriving them of their rights to education, a dignified life in society and other social, economic and political advantages. It is pitiful that they cannot even be allowed to explore their hidden potential and hone their skills and abilities in order to find a means of income is similar with (Jazeel, 2017). individualized learning plans and accommodations play a crucial role in ensuring that all students have the opportunity to reach their full potential. By tailoring instruction to meet the needs of each individual student and providing necessary accommodations, educators can support a diverse range of learners and create an inclusive and supportive learning environment. Ultimately, these tools help to promote academic success, boost confidence and foster a sense of belonging among students.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the discourse around differently abled students and education emphasize the importance of creating inclusive environments that accommodate diverse learning needs. The opportunities for differently abled students in receiving higher education have significantly improved, yet challenges remain. With advancements in

technology and growing awareness of inclusivity, educational institutions are better equipped to provide the necessary accommodations, such as assistive technologies, accessible campuses and tailored support services. Barriers such as inadequate physical infrastructure, limited access to assistive technologies and a lack of tailored support services continue to hinder their educational experience. Furthermore, social stigmas and biases can create an unwelcoming environment, making it difficult for these students to fully participate in academic and social activities. These challenges not only impact their academic success but also affect their overall well-being and sense of belonging within the educational community. This includes investing in accessible infrastructure, providing comprehensive support services and promoting awareness and understanding of the needs of differently abled students. By doing so, higher education can become more equitable, ensuring that all students, regardless of their abilities, have the opportunity to succeed and contribute to their communities. Therefore, it is essential for institutions, policymakers and society to work collaboratively to address these challenges. The study recommends to develop comprehensive curriculum frameworks that address the specific educational needs of differently abled students and enhance students training and professional development programs to equip educators with the skills and knowledge needed to support higher education practices. It should be policy changes that promote accessibility, inclusion and equitable opportunities for differently abled students in educational institutions.

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